

Research Rabbit

Introduction

Research Rabbit is a cutting-edge web application that helps professionals, researchers, and students plan literature reviews as efficiently as possible. By eliminating the need to move between search modes and databases, this user-friendly "citation-based literature mapping tool" improves the effectiveness of your research and saves you a significant amount of time. Users only need to enter one or more seed papers into the system to get going. Based on the topic of interest determined by your initial selections, Research Rabbit's sophisticated algorithm then produces a variety of pertinent documents. By doing away with the frequently tiresome and time-consuming citation mining procedure, this feature seeks to keep users' research efforts efficient and focused.

By sending pertinent literature straight to the user, Research Rabbit's core function is to expedite and simplify the research process. Your research trip will be supported by the intuitive features and user-friendly interface, which will keep you ahead of the curve on your academic or professional assignment. Additionally, researchers can use Research Rabbit for free.

Advantage:

- As opposed to selling your own work back to you, the tool is dedicated to furthering human knowledge by empowering researchers in the most effective manner possible.
- They keep improving their array of technologies in accordance with their mission-first philosophy.
- Research Rabbit is a creative method to maximize academic research and is a useful and adaptable tool for professionals, writers, and students throughout the world.
- It makes the difficult process of conducting a literature review easier and more manageable.
- There are numerous literature mapping tools on the internet, including ResearchRabbit; some demand account creation, while others do not. ResearchRabbit is available for free.

History

ResearchRabbit is an artificial intelligence (AI)-powered application for finding scholarly publications. A three-person team in Seattle created it in 2021. With the use of visualization maps and lists of previous, later, and related publications, this tool enables users to find publications that are related to one or more seed papers. ResearchRabbit is made to facilitate unstructured search workflows by offering a left-to-right path from the originating publication or publications via any chosen authors or publications. The tool's name may have come from these trails, which can go as deep as rabbit holes.

Features

- **A Literature Mapping Tool Based on Citations**

ResearchRabbit is an online program that helps you identify relevant literature by using a "seed paper" approach. You can enter one or more research papers, and it will find other relevant papers for you. This will save you time when conducting research.

- **Team with a mission:**

ResearchRabbit is dedicated to providing researchers with free access, both now and in the future, as part of its mission to further human understanding.

- **A Novel Approach to Searching:**

makes the research process quicker and more effective by doing away with the need to switch between different databases and searching modes.

- **Copyrighted Content:**

ResearchRabbit protects intellectual property by copyrighting all of its content.

- **Enhanced Keyword Lookup:**

To obtain pertinent information and navigate the website with ease, enter your keyword.

Step by step tutorial :

Step 1

Go to <https://researchrabbitapp.com/> and register. There is no cost.

The image shows a registration form for ResearchRabbit. At the top is a wireframe logo of a rabbit. Below it are two input fields: 'Email' and 'Password'. To the right of the 'Password' field is a blue 'Log In' button. Below the 'Password' field is a link that says 'Forgot/Change Password'. At the bottom of the form is a large blue 'Sign Up' button.

Step 2

You can choose a reference paper to begin your research by clicking on +Add Papers. Include a study that you are certain is important to your inquiry. You can include a single paper or several.

To demonstrate the process, I will upload a paper titled "Information seeking behaviour" as an example. Once you choose the paper and search for it using the title, you can add it to your collection (see picture below). You can work on multiple projects at once because you can create multiple collections and rename them. The reference paper you choose will show up in the app with the abstract, author name, title, year of publication, and journal where the paper was published. The app also displays the number of similar papers that have been found online, as well as an exploration of the references and citations in the paper you selected.

Step 3

You can see the most accurate and close relationship between your reference document and the web literature by selecting "Similar work."

- Now, all related works are arranged in order of importance. They can also be sorted alphabetically or by citations.
- When you check the "abstracts" box, the app will display the abstracts of all related works that are mentioned. This will make it simple for you to go through the results and determine which publications are truly pertinent to your research and which are not.
- Choose the graph type in the connection graph that best fits your study.

If you want to talk about your topic in chronological order, a timeline graph type might be helpful, but a network type will highlight similarities between references.

- If you are interested in looking at different authors, the "labels" option can be helpful as it may lead to the discovery of additional publications and alternative paths.

Step 4 :

You can now begin expanding your investigation after identifying your primary links. All of the papers that could be pertinent to your project are presented in blue, while the papers that are part of your collection are shown in green. You can add the papers you think are pertinent to your collection as you go through the references. After that, these papers will be shown in green, and further links will be made on their own.

By just clicking on the author's name on the graph, you can add papers from it to your collection. The chosen paper will then open with the complete abstract displayed on the right side of the graph. The new paper can then be added to your collection by selecting the "Add

to" option. The graph changes as soon as the paper is added to the collection, and other related work and relationships will show up.

You can now add as many papers as you like to your collection and continue developing your research. In addition to creating several collections, you can use them to divide up paragraphs and themes to avoid complicating your search.

You can also view the same visualization in the timeline view, which, as you might expect, shows you a similar visualization with blue nodes representing papers in the list you are

currently considering and green nodes representing papers in your collection. The only difference is that the year of publication is now represented by the vertical axis.

The screenshot displays a research interface with several panels:

- Left Panel:** A sidebar with a search bar and a list of papers. One paper is selected: "How are we searching the world wide web?: a comparison of nine search engine transaction logs" by Jansen and Spink, published in 2006.
- Similar Work Panel:** A list of papers related to the selected one. The top entry is "Are people biased in their use of search engines" by Keane and Smyth (2008). Other entries include "Standard parameters for searching behaviour in search engines and their empirical evaluation" by Höchstötter and Koch (2009), and "Suchmaschinen als Konkurrenten der Bibliothekskataloge - Wie Bibliotheken ihre Angebote durch Suchmaschinentechnologie attraktiver und durch Öffnung für die allgemeinen Suchmaschinen populärer machen können" by Lewandowski (2006).
- Network Graph Panel:** A network graph titled "Connections between your collection and 50 papers". It shows a complex web of nodes (papers) connected by lines. The nodes are color-coded by year, with 2006 nodes being green and others blue. The graph is filtered to show connections between the selected paper and 50 others.
- Right Panel:** A sidebar with "EXPLORE PEOPLE" and "EXPLORE OTHER CONTENT" sections. "These Authors" shows 209 authors, and "Suggested Authors" shows 439 authors. "EXPLORE OTHER CONTENT" shows 63 linked content items.

Step 5

An exciting option is the suggested author, which automatically opens a co-authorship network and uses an unidentified algorithm to recommend some writers you might find interesting. It also displays the authors' most recent affiliations in a list.

The screenshot displays a research interface with several panels:

- Left Panel:** A sidebar with a search bar and a list of papers. One paper is selected: "How are we searching the world wide web?: a comparison of nine search engine transaction logs" by Jansen and Spink, published in 2006.
- These Authors Panel:** A list of authors recommended by the system. The top entry is Dirk Lewandowski, affiliated with Hamburg University of Applied Sciences, with 159 publications and 1274 citations. Other authors listed include Thorsten Joachims (Cornell University, 255 publications, 49122 citations), Laura Granka (Google, 23 publications, 4526 citations), Amanda Spink (Queensland University of Technology, 319 publications, 12862 citations), and Marco Maggini (University of Siena, 169 publications, 2067 citations).
- Network Graph Panel:** A network graph titled "Connections between 63 authors". It shows a complex web of nodes (authors) connected by lines. The nodes are color-coded by year, with 2006 nodes being green and others blue. The graph is filtered to show connections between the selected author and 63 others.
- Right Panel:** A sidebar with "EXPLORE PEOPLE" and "EXPLORE OTHER CONTENT" sections. "These Authors" shows 209 authors, and "Suggested Authors" shows 439 authors. "EXPLORE OTHER CONTENT" shows 63 linked content items.

one can see how identifying authors who could merit more research could be intriguing. Curiously, though, the co-authorship graph now uses red to emphasize all writers.

In order to give you the option of focusing more on or ignoring writers who have already written papers in your collection, I think it could be a good idea to highlight them in a different color. The present paper network, where the collected papers are green, is comparable to this. However, it's obvious that there is room for more growth in this area.

Limitation

1. It can be intimidating to explore all of ResearchRabbit's capabilities. To fully utilize ResearchRabbit, a significant initial time commitment is necessary to become familiar with its various capabilities.
2. Users are left to recall which branching routes of authors and citations they have already investigated because ResearchRabbit now restricts exploration to a single linear path. Unless the publications are in one of the user's collections, the interface does not allow users to mark publications they have already encountered or store a rabbit hole for subsequent exploration.
3. Author disambiguation is a problem for the author visualization maps. A single author frequently appears in ResearchRabbit as two nodes in a collaborative network, each of which is linked to a distinct publication and citation number.

Conclusion

The wide number of features that ResearchRabbit provides can initially be daunting. However, ResearchRabbit can develop into a potent discovery tool for academics conducting unstructured searches after users get beyond the learning curve. Diverse users' needs are met by the numerous kinds of maps that can be created and the various views that are available in each map. Its usage of AI distinguishes its publication recommendations from those of its rivals and offers customers a wider selection of suggested publications than they otherwise would.

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